

State policy regarding the psychological adaptation of internally displaced persons from the eastern regions of Ukraine

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Abstract. The article examines aspects of the state policy of Ukraine in the psychological adaptation of temporarily displaced persons who fled in 2014 from the areas of hostilities in the Donetsk and Lugansk regions of Ukraine. The analysis of the legal framework of Ukraine regarding the psychological adaptation of temporarily displaced persons after their arrival at a new place of residence is carried out. Revealed the attitude of temporarily displaced persons to government bodies. The main directions of improvement of state mechanisms of psychological adaptation of temporarily displaced persons in Ukraine are proposed.

1 Introduction

For the past five years, the Ukrainian state has been daily faced with the need to resist external military aggression. With the outbreak of hostilities in part of the territory of Donetsk and Lugansk regions of Ukraine since 2014, a large number of civilians in these areas were forced to leave their homes and move to other regions of Ukraine. According to official data from the UN Refugee Agency, at the end of 2019, 1,415,635 Ukrainian citizens had the status of “internally displaced persons”: 489775 internally displaced persons were registered in the Donetsk region, 275947 in Luhansk, and 131998 in Kharkiv region [1]. However, in reality the number of such people is much higher, since many of the displaced persons are not registered with social services.

This problem is typical not only for Ukraine, but also for the whole world, especially where military conflicts arise, local hostilities are conducted. In recent years, the countries of the European Union have also experienced serious difficulties associated with the uncontrolled flow of refugees from Africa and the Middle East. Scientific studies show that the mental health of refugees and their behavior is becoming a serious problem for the host countries, since most refugees stay for years or even decades and try to obtain a permanent residence permit by any means [2].

In situations where a person is forced to leave his place of permanent residence, and this needs to be done in a very short time, then he experiences only negative emotions. Very often these emotions are long lasting, which leads to a deterioration in the mental state and overall health of a person. It has been proven that the psychological state of the individual, the mental health of refugees, their deviant and addictive behavior is often a problem for psychiatrists, psychologists, as well as representatives of government bodies of countries that have accepted refugees [3]. Researchers note that half of the refugees show signs of post-traumatic stress disorder [4]. The psychological stress constantly experienced by refugees at the stage of adaptation to new living conditions sharply worsens their quality of

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life [5, 6, 7]. The difficulties and problems of refugees, which they face when integrating into a new cultural environment, are investigated [8, 9, 10].

It is noted that the adaptation process to a large extent depends on the psychological state of the person undergoing adaptation. One of the main conditions for successful psychological adaptation is a benevolent attitude towards the social environment in which a person undergoes adaptation [11]. If a person has a negative attitude towards her, then the success of psychological adaptation to new conditions of existence cannot be successful.

Purpose of the study: to reveal the features of the state policy of Ukraine in relation to the psychological adaptation of forced migrants from the eastern regions of Ukraine. Research objectives: (1) to establish the influence of the state on the process of psychological adaptation of internally displaced persons who fled hostilities in the territory of Luhansk and Donetsk regions of Ukraine; (2) to reveal the peculiarities of the emotional state of internally displaced persons and their attitude towards the state authorities; (3) to determine the main directions for improving the process of psychological adaptation of internally displaced persons to new conditions of life.

2 Materials and methods

Content analysis of the legislative framework of Ukraine was used to study aspects of psychological adaptation of internally displaced persons.

The study of the attitude of internally displaced persons to government authorities was attended by 3,500 socially active people who moved from the occupied territories of Donetsk and Luhansk regions to the territory controlled by Ukraine. Age of respondents: 25-50 years old. The study was conducted during the second half of 2014 (after the outbreak of hostilities) - November 2016.

All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the National Scientific Center for Medical and Biotechnical Research of the NAS of Ukraine, based on the Helsinki Declaration of 1964 and its subsequent amendments. Informed consent was sought from all the participants. Moreover, almost all (90% of the respondents) asked to hide their true names and surnames.

To determine the attitude of internally displaced persons towards the state authorities of Ukraine, we used Etkind's "Color Test of Relationship" (CTO) methodology [13] and personal interviews with displaced persons. For this, stimulating material was developed and the following concepts were proposed: "President of Ukraine", "Government of Ukraine", "Local authority in the point of permanent residence", "Social service", "Local community of the new place of residence of internally displaced persons", "Volunteer". The choice of methodology was determined by the fact that many internally displaced persons were reluctant to make psychological contact with the researcher, wanting to remain anonymous. The regions of Ukraine from which internally displaced persons have moved are bilingual, where Russian and Ukrainian languages are used. Therefore, the interview was conducted in Ukrainian or Russian, the choice of which was determined by the respondent.

3 Results and discussion

At the first stage of the study, a content analysis of the laws of Ukraine was carried out, which deal with adaptation issues. Terminological confusion in a number of legislative and normative documents regulating human activity under conditions of existential threat always leads to their inadequate interpretation [15-24].

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Approaches to the definition of the term “adaptation” accepted all over the world distinguish the following types of it: physiological, mental, socio-psychological, psychophysiological and professional adaptation [14]. An analysis of Ukrainian legislation gives grounds to assert that the use of the term "psychological adaptation" in Ukrainian legislation has a slightly different content. First, this term is used by Ukrainian legislators only in one document, the Law of Ukraine "On the rehabilitation of disabled people in Ukraine", which was adopted in 2005 [12]. Secondly, the comparison of the content of the term "psychological adaptation", which is used in world science and in the legislation of our country, made it possible to identify the main difference: the Ukrainian society, guided by existing laws and other regulatory legal documents, depersonalizes work with those people who need close attention from professional psychologists within the framework of the problem under consideration.

State authorities of Ukraine adapt internally displaced persons to the existing conditions and requirements in society, instead of allowing people to satisfy their urgent needs and realize significant goals associated with them. Analysis of the activities of state structures in the first period of mass movement of people from certain parts of the Donetsk and Luhansk regions of Ukraine in 2014 gives grounds to assert some mistakes. It is precisely in the terminological confusion that the main mistake in organizing assistance to internally displaced persons lies: the state bodies tried to adapt the displaced persons to the existing reality, forgetting that it is the state that should help to satisfy their urgent needs, such as the need for food, home, and most importantly, for security. After all, the destruction of the usual way of life, disorganization, disorientation, loss of a sense of security, self-confidence, in the future causes a person to fear death. Having survived the horrors of armed confrontation, having lost not only something material, but also confidence in the future, people were forced to flee from their small homeland in order to save precious things - their lives and the lives of their loved ones.

Thus, after such events, a psychologically traumatized personality is formed who does not know what awaits her, what to hope for and how to proceed. Therefore, practically all internally displaced persons need psychological assistance at the stage of moving to a new place of residence. But this assistance must be provided to varying degrees, taking into account the mental trauma of internally displaced persons.

An analysis of the circumstances that forced internally displaced persons to leave their permanent place of residence made it possible to formulate the following classification of internally displaced persons and the need for psychological assistance:

- 1) left the combat zone in advance, with things, documents, etc. - need only social assistance (resettlement, documents, employment);
- 2) left the combat zone quickly, not all of the things were taken away, came under fire - they need psychological help in a group form - debriefing the stress of a critical incident;
- 3) came under fire, housing was destroyed partially or completely - in need of material and psychological assistance;
- 4) have been in the combat zone for a long time (more than 6 months) - they need psychological help;
- 5) family members remained in the combat zone - they need psychological help;
- 6) themselves were injured or family members - in need of psychological assistance;
- 7) the death of a loved one in a combat zone - they need material and psychological assistance.

Items 1-2 will characterize internally displaced persons in whom a successful process of psychological adaptation can be predicted in the future. Items 3-7 characterize people who need psychological help and special psychological attention from psychologists. It is

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necessary to be very careful in predicting the success of their passage through the process of psychological adaptation to new conditions of life. It should be noted that all internally displaced persons who are in need of psychological assistance also need social and material assistance without fail.

Thus, a mandatory measure should be the preliminary differentiation of internally displaced persons into groups or categories of victims, the main criterion for which will be the nature of the losses suffered by the person and the degree of psychological traumatization of the individual.

At the second stage of the study, the attitude of internally displaced persons towards government bodies was revealed using the TEC and personal interviews with internally displaced persons. It was found that the results of the interviews correlate with the data obtained using the TEC. The generalized results of the TEC methodology and interviews are presented in Figures 1, 2.

1 - "President of Ukraine", 2 - "Government of Ukraine", 3 - "Local authorities in the point of permanent residence", 4 - "Social service", 5 - "Local community of the new place of residence of internally displaced persons", 6 - "Volunteer" .

Fig. 1. Generalized result of positive attitudes of internally displaced persons towards incentives (%).

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1 - "President of Ukraine", 2 - "Government of Ukraine", 3 - "Local authorities in the point of permanent residence", 4 - "Social service", 5 - "Local community of the new place of residence of internally displaced persons", 6 - "Volunteer" .

Fig. 2. Generalized result of negative attitudes of internally displaced persons towards incentives (%).

According to respondents, the Government of Ukraine evokes the most negative emotional attitude among internally displaced persons. Most likely, this is due to the fact that, in their opinion, it is precisely it that is to blame for the fact that hostilities began on the territory of a part of the Donetsk and Luhansk regions. According to the results of the interview, it was clarified that internally displaced persons are accused of unprofessionalism by all the authorities existing in 2014 in Ukraine. At the same time, it is not specified who is to blame (the Cabinet of Ministers, the Supreme Council, the Prime Minister, the Speaker of the Supreme Council, etc.), but it is indicated as a whole: "the power of Ukraine is to blame for the war".

Internally displaced persons are treated more positively to the President of Ukraine. This is explained by the fact that at the beginning of hostilities in Donetsk and Luhansk regions in 2014, the current head of state of Ukraine was only elected. He was not blamed for what happened. Internally displaced persons are showing hope that the President of Ukraine will be able to stop the hostilities and that the internally displaced persons will return to their places of permanent residence.

The hostilities forced a large number of people in a very short time to collect only the necessary things, documents, jewelry and leave for an unknown place, the main thing - away from the war. Many IDPs believe that the local authorities at the point of permanent residence have not done enough to organize resettlement. Also, many IDPs accuse local authorities of preventing the outbreak of hostilities.

It was revealed that the attitude towards social services is neutral, more negative. During the interviews, many internally displaced persons believed that social workers did their work poorly, reluctantly. Such calls usually did not bring the expected result, the resolution of the issue was delayed, often making the call to the service itself meaningless. According to some internally displaced persons (44%), social workers sometimes solved problems. The respondents noted that social services work better in large settlements than in small ones.

The attitude towards the local community of the new place of residence of internally displaced persons depended on whether the displaced persons were able to quickly adapt to the new living conditions. If internally displaced persons adapt quickly, then the attitude towards the new community is good. Conversely, this was especially evident in a situation where internally displaced persons at their main place of residence lived in the city, and he was resettled in the countryside.

The most positive attitudes of internally displaced persons were towards volunteers. It was they who greatly helped many internally displaced persons to find new housing, to acquire the necessary personal belongings and household items. With the help of volunteers, many internally displaced persons were able to quickly adapt to new living conditions and find work.

The main directions for improving the process of psychological adaptation to the new conditions of life of people who have received the status of internally displaced persons can be as follows.

At the first stage (arrival and resettlement of internally displaced persons), psychologists and social workers should classify internally displaced persons and plan individual measures for social and psychological assistance. The most trained specialists should work

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at this stage. Today, such specialists are representatives of the psychological service of the State Emergency Service of Ukraine (State Service of Ukraine for Emergency Situations). It is she who is entrusted with the duty of psychological protection of the population in situations of emergencies of a natural, technogenic, social and military nature.

Our personal long-term experience of working with various categories of the affected population (2014-2019) allows us to state that only social support is enough for some victims. Here we can predict a positive adaptation to new conditions of life. In this case, the provided social support can eliminate the need for psychological assistance when going through the process of human adaptation to new conditions of life. And other internally displaced persons who have suffered more severe losses will need long-term psychological rehabilitation. In this case, there will be a fairly long process of experiencing losses and "living" grief. It must be emphasized that until the basic needs of a person are satisfied, it is pointless to organize and carry out measures of psychological adaptation.

Thus, the internally displaced persons, who belong to the 1st group of victims we have identified, will by themselves have the motivation to "live on", overcome difficulties, and rely on something. Therefore, it will be enough for such migrants to carry out activities within the framework of social and psychological stimulation to be active, coordination of actions, information, etc.

Migrants who belong to the 2nd group of internally displaced persons, having lost the meaning of life, disillusioned with those around them, lose their desire to overcome difficulties on their own. Such people are distinguished by a passive position, fear of the future, actualization of the past, indifference to everything that happens to them, and sometimes suicidal thoughts can arise.

The aforementioned traits in the behavior of internally displaced persons are some kind of markers that psychologists must pay attention to, especially during correctional and rehabilitation measures.

In addition to differentiating internally displaced persons by the nature and degree of their psychological traumatization, we must also take into account the categories of victims: a child, an elderly person, a woman or a man. This should also be taken into account when organizing psychological work.

Scientists of the Research Laboratory of Extreme and Crisis Psychology of the National University of Civil Protection of Ukraine have developed new approaches to organizing psychological assistance to the victims of the Donetsk and Lugansk regions of Ukraine and determined:

- types of losses and their impact on internally displaced persons;
- features of the experience of the victims of the loss of housing as a result of the current situation;
- the main behavioral responses of women who have lost their husbands;
- basic behavioral responses of men who have lost their wife;
 - the main behavioral reactions of elderly persons who have lost their wife or husband;
- peculiarities of behavior of victims who survived the loss of a child;
 - the main types of victims' response to loss in ATO conditions and their psychological analysis.

Psychologists of the CSNS should carry out work within the framework of the initial (that is, urgent, but not perfect) psychological adaptation of migrants at the stage of the IDP's exit from the zone of existential threat and transfer it to psychologists from other public and private organizations for further psychological support.

Having collected data on each specific person, psychologists must decide on the procedure for providing the victim with one or another type of assistance. Here, at the state

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level, the problem of organizing the interaction of specialists from various ministries and departments that are involved in this process should be solved. Its solution should be in the form of a system of clear interaction of all organizations, associations, divisions and services that are involved in providing psychological assistance to internally displaced persons, both "vertically" and "horizontally". It is necessary to determine a coordinating body for the provision of psychological assistance and develop an algorithm for cooperation between specialists-psychologists of state and non-state organizations.

The second echelon in interdepartmental interaction should involve fellow psychologists from other ministries and departments at the stage of an injured person leaving the danger zone. Further coordination of interaction between internally displaced persons and practical psychologists should be carried out by specialists of the Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine.

Note that in every region of Ukraine there are state rehabilitation centers. But the overwhelming majority of internally displaced persons prefer non-state centers in which rehabilitation, including psychological adaptation, is carried out. The negative attitude of internally displaced persons towards state rehabilitation centers does not make it possible to carry out high-quality measures for psychological rehabilitation and adaptation. Probably, this explains the increase in rehabilitation centers for internally displaced persons, established on a volunteer basis.

There is another unresolved problem in Ukraine in the field of organizing and carrying out psychological adaptation of internally displaced persons. Based on our experience of working with victims of various emergencies, it can be argued that when volunteer psychologists were involved in providing assistance to this category of people, half were not ready to work: the use of the usual algorithms of the "academic" approach and working methods were absolutely unacceptable for work in emergency conditions.

Psychologists, who are responsible for providing psychological assistance to internally displaced persons, must necessarily have not only a classical psychological education, but also possess the basics of extreme and crisis psychology, and know the peculiarities of the course and dynamics of the mental state of a person who has experienced a traumatic event.

4 Conclusions from the conducted research

The mental health and behavior of internally displaced persons is essential for the normal functioning of the communities in which they have moved. To organize the psychological adaptation of internally displaced persons, it is necessary to develop a legislative framework taking into account international scientific approaches to the definition of the term "psychological adaptation". At the stage of arrival and resettlement of internally displaced persons, a classification of internally displaced persons should be carried out and individual social and psychological assistance activities should be planned.

The study showed that the most negative attitude among the majority of internally displaced persons (85%) is caused by the Government of Ukraine, and among half of the respondents - by social services and local government bodies. The highest level of trust of internally displaced persons is shown to volunteers who really helped to find new housing, to acquire the necessary personal belongings and household items.

Governments at all levels need to broaden their awareness and education among internally displaced persons. Taking into account the negative attitude of internally displaced persons towards state rehabilitation programs, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for financial support of non-state centers for the adaptation of internally displaced persons to the new conditions of their life. The practical implementation at the

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state level of a system of providing social and psychological assistance to internally displaced persons will allow for more effective psychological adaptation of internally displaced persons.

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